

The Possibility of Lithium Iodide (LiI) as H₂ Storage Material: A Conceptual DFT (CDFT) Approach

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Abstract:

This article deals with the different types of the hydrogen storage process, its thermochemistry, adsorption process, and binding energy, in the light of the computational approach using the conceptual density functional theory (CDFT). This article expresses the view that lithium iodide (LiI) is a viable template for hydrogen storage at low temperatures. The density functional theory (DFT) has been used to investigate the structure and chemical reactivity of the resulting templates. The adsorption process is found to be quasi-sorption in nature. The molecular hydrogen interacts with building blocks (with Li centre) through electrovalent interaction and a single LiI molecule is capable of absorbing 10 H₂ with a high gravimetric wt% value (13.07 wt%) which is found to be a promising system as per standard. The changes in Gibbs free energy indicate that hydrogen adsorption can occur spontaneously at cryogenic temperatures.

Keywords: LiI; Computational Study; Hydrogen adsorption; Binding Energy; Quasi-sorption, Gravimetric wt%.

List of Abbreviations:

PES (Potential energy surface); CDFT (Conceptual density functional theory); HOMO (Highest occupied molecular orbital); LUMO (Lowest unoccupied molecular orbital); NPA (Natural population analysis); NBO (Natural bond orbital); NAOs (natural atomic orbitals); DOE (U.S. Department of Energy); ELF (Electron localization function); AIM (Atoms in Molecules); QTAIM (Quantum theory of atoms in molecules); BCP (Bond critical points)

1. Introduction

A high level of consumption of energy sources such as coal, oil, and natural gas is contributing to both the acceleration of global warming and the depletion of these resources at a reasonable rate. Because that is a fixed source, which means that every day we extract them from the mines and eventually they will run out, and also because when we burn this particular coal, or perhaps the oils, they create huge toxic gases.^[1-3] So basically they are going into the environment and which causes problems to the human health, or perhaps the pollution to mankind, and so on. Renewable resources such as solar, hydrogen, biomass, and geothermal are now being rapidly developed throughout the globe. Renewable energy comes from natural processes or non-depletable resources such as sunlight or water.^[4-7] Thus, we can harness this form of energy and attempt to transform it into usable electrical power. The sun isn't the only source of energy we rely on; hydrogen, biomass, and geothermal power all play crucial roles as well. Hydrogen, among other options, is widely acknowledged as the best energy transporter and greenest energy option. Hence, if we are successful in capturing that

hydrogen, then we might be able to use it as a fuel in the future. The solid-state is a far more trustworthy mode of storage when compared to the liquid and gaseous states, both in terms of safety concerns and capacity in volumetric terms. Yet, transporting a container large enough to hold hydrogen in a liquid or, more likely, a gaseous form has its own set of challenges.^[8] Not only must such a container be leakproof, but the material used to create it must also be durable enough to last. It should sustain high pressure or may be sometimes temperature. Hydrogen can be stored either in a gaseous state or in a liquid state. Hydrogen gas storage typically requires the use of high-pressure tanks (350-700 bar, 5000-10000psi) while liquid hydrogen storage requires the temperature to prevent it from boiling back into a gas (which occurs at -252.8°C). Hydrogen can also be stored on a solid surface (adsorption) in solid materials.^[1-7] Hydrogen storage is a key enabling technology for the advancement of hydrogen and fuel technologies in the application including stationary power, portable power, and transportation. Enabling technology means enabling the use of various forms of devices and technologies to support a person with disabilities to live as independently as possible. These types of technology are in mobile applications, sensors, and other smart devices.

2. Types of Hydrogen

Green Hydrogen: Hydrogen obtained by electrolysis of water is considered "green" hydrogen. Only hydrogen and oxygen are created in this process. In the chemical industry, it is often utilised in the production of ammonia and fertilisers.^[9-10]

Yellow Hydrogen: The term "yellow hydrogen" describes hydrogen created using a combination of renewable and fossil fuel sources. Hydrogen is generated here by electrolyzing water using sunlight.^[9-10]

Pink Hydrogen: Electrolysis driven by nuclear energy produces the pink hydrogen. It's utilised in the processing of oil, the creation of methanol, and the manufacture of steel.^[9-10]

White Hydrogen: White hydrogen is produced by-product of an industrial process or the hydrogen produced by the gasification of renewable sources like biomass.^[9-10]

2. Different methods of Hydrogen storage

A number of different methods exist for storing hydrogen, including (a) high-pressure gas cylinders, (b) liquid hydrogen in a cryogenic tank, (c) hydrogen adsorbed on materials with a large specific surface area (at $T < 100\text{K}$), and (d) hydrogen absorbed on interstitial sites in a host metal (at ambient temperature). Much attention has been paid to hydrogen as a fuel that can aid the transportation industry in becoming carbon neutral.

2.1. Storage in the Liquid form

Hydrogen can be stored chemically, liquidly, or in its gaseous state. So, we may conclude that vehicles with limited space that need energy power or fast speed will benefit from using liquid hydrogen as a fuel. Therefore, an analytical investigation of liquid hydrogen tank thermal insulation for cryogenic storage is required. Cryogenic hydrogen storage necessitates extremely low temperatures to prevent the liquid hydrogen from reverting to a gas at almost -252.8°C .^[11,12] The energy required for cooling and compressing the liquid hydrogen results in a net loss of around 30% of the energy contained in the hydrogen itself. Storage tanks are fortified and insulated to resist pressure and high temperatures. Regularly throughout a longer period of time. There is still active study in the subject of liquid hydrogen storage, with an emphasis on the improvement of the composite tank, materials, and liquefaction processes. Good low-temperature performance is a key feature of austenitic stainless steel, making it the material of choice for liquid hydrogen storage and transport tanks. Hydrogen has a volumetric energy density of 71 kg/m^3 when stored as a liquid at a temperature of -252.9°C , demonstrating

its excellent storage capability during this phase. In virtually all cases, hydrogen is

employed as a fuel when combined with another gas so as to have a low reaction energy. When combined with an oxidizer like liquid oxygen, liquid hydrogen produces the highest specific impulse (or efficiency) of any rocket fuel. It takes roughly 13% of the hydrogen's entire energy content to compress it, and about 40% of that to liquefy it. Inflammability is a major concern when dealing with hydrogen gas. Hydrogen gas may damage metals if it escapes confinement.^[13]

2.2. Storage in the compressed gas form:

Hydrogen gas may be stored in high-pressure tanks. To accomplish compression, more energy is required. The compressed gas takes up a lot of room, thus the compression vessels need to be checked often to make sure there are no leaks. If not, we can just blow it. To store hydrogen, compressed form is more cost effective than liquid form.^[14]

3. Advantages and disadvantages of Hydrogen as fuel

Several different types of domestic resources may be used to create hydrogen, and this might lead to the development of technologies that emit no greenhouse gases at all. Hydrogen, once created, may be used to power fuel cells, which convert the chemical energy into electricity while releasing only water vapour and heat. It has potential for development in both the fixed and mobile energy markets. There are certain disadvantages also, like- (a) Hydrogen energy is expensive; (b) it has storage complications (c) and carrying problems in moving instruments, vehicles, and automobiles.

4. Key Challenges

The kind of materials mainly used for hydrogen storage includes carbon -base materials including nanotubes carbon. Transition metal, organic metal frameworks, C(MOFS), etc. All the materials have high specific surface areas but exhibit weak binding forces with hydrogen (mostly by van der Waal forces). A great deal of resources depicts that metal decoration (including alkali, alkaline part, and transition metals) is effective to increase the binding energy of hydrogen on sorption-based materials. So that the materials on hydrogen can stick with the surface or may be chemisorption it can go inside. Hydrogen storage in carbon materials is increased by the decoration of these materials with transition metals because of hydrogen spillover phenomena. Hydrogen gas is as low as 0.08988 g/L at room temperature and atmospheric pressure^[15] which is very problematic in its storage to be economically viable. Hence the only task is to increase its storage density. Several methods have been proposed to store hydrogen at increased density but no one has proven to be efficient till date.^[16] A specific method always has a substantial influence on the capital and operating costs of the storage.^[17,18] Due to the different constraints, there is room for more than one technological option for large-scale hydrogen storage.^[19] There are mostly three major methods of storage of hydrogen that have been developed so far. First one, storage of hydrogen gas at high pressure at room temperature (RT), second, storage of hydrogen at low temperature in the liquid phase and third; storage of hydrogen in the solid phase through adsorption at low or RT. And subsequently, all these methods have their own advantages-disadvantages.^[20] There is a huge infrastructural burden always associated with the storage of hydrogen in high pressure at room temperature. On the other hand, it is also very difficult to store and transportation of hydrogen in the liquid phase. Hence it would be a better option to store the same as an absorbed material. It's easy to see that at normal temperature, solid hydrogen has a negligible adsorption percentage (just 2-3%). Our team is investigating

potential solutions for enhanced hydrogen adsorption in the solid state. Hydrogen may be stored in solid materials in two ways, physisorption and chemisorption, with a number of candidate materials having been theoretically predicted.^[21] Although hydrogen may be desorbed at room temperature via a physisorption process, this method is not suitable for storing large amounts of the gas. Instead, chemisorption appears to be an easy and efficient approach to store a significant amount of hydrogen. As chemisorption is not reversible, it does not meet the requirements for storage.^[22] Thus, it is necessary to investigate a novel, potentially useful storage technique in which the adsorption-desorption mechanism of hydrogen is reversible and the concerned energy is between that of physisorption and chemisorption (quasi-sorption).^[23-25] We recently disclosed some potential hydrogen storage materials, which can fulfil the objective set by the United States Department of Energy (DOE), 2015. With all of these considerations in mind, we came up with these materials.^[26] We recently reported (using a computational approach) the surprising hydrogen storage efficacy of lithium fluoride (LiF),^[27] lithium chloride (LiCl), and lithium bromide (LiBr),^[28] which prompted us to revisit the topic with lithium iodide (LiI) in order to determine which of these materials was the most effective.

5. Role of different parameters for establishing a material to be an ideal H₂ storage material and conceptual density functional theory (CDFT)

5.1. Geometry optimization, Gaussian 16w and GaussView 6

Geometry optimization, in the field of computational chemistry, is locating an arrangement of atoms in space such that the net inter-atomic force acting on each atom is negligible and the atoms' positions on the potential energy surface (PES) are fixed.^[29] Many experimental and theoretical research involving chemical structure, thermodynamics, chemical kinetics, spectroscopy, and others can benefit from the optimal geometry of such a system.^[29] As an example, LiI and its H₂ adsorbed systems [Fig. 1]. For optimization purposes, we have used Gaussian 16w.^[30] GaussView 6^[31] shows the results of calculations in a way that is natural and easy to understand.

5.2. conceptual density functional theory (CDFT), functional and basis set

In this section, we talk about the conceptual density functional theory (CDFT),^[32,33] which is a very popular theoretical model, and how it can be used to set up more precise mathematical relationships between reactive parameters and bonding in molecular structures. Conceptual density functional theory (CDFT) has proven to be a strong methodology for understanding molecular reactivity. Several hybrid functionals, which include a mixture of Hartree-Fock exchange with DFT exchange-correlation, are available via keywords-

B3LYP: Hartree-Fock exchange, local exchange, gradient exchange correction, local correlation, and gradient correlation correction are all components of B3LYP (Becke, 3-parameter, Lee–Yang–Parr),^[34] the most well-known hybrid density functional theory model.

Functionals Including Long-Range-Corrected Functionals and dispersion-

Exchange functionals can't be used to model processes like electrons jumping to high orbitals because the non-Coulomb part of them dies off too quickly and gets very wrong at large distances. Different plans have been made to deal with these kinds of situations. Gaussian 16 has the following functions, which include long-range corrections. In optimization of LiI@nH₂ (n= 1-10), we have used these two following long-range corrected functions which have been elaborately stated below.

CAM-B3LYP: Handy and his coworkers used the Coulomb-attenuating method to make a

long-range version of B3LYP.^[32,33]

wB97XD: The most recent functional developed by Head-Gordon and his colleagues, incorporates empirical dispersion.^[32,33] Grimme's D2 dispersion model is used in the wB97XD

functional. One can also get the wB97 and wB97X versions. Long-range corrections are also part of these functionals.

For effective computer implementation in theoretical and computational chemistry, partial differential equations must be transformed into algebraic equations using a basis set^[35] that describes the electronic wave function according to the Hartree-Fock technique or density-functional theory. **LanL2DZ** (Los Alamos National Laboratory 2 double- ζ), which is a commonly used effective core potential (ECP)-type basis set^[35], was used to model the metal atoms. In optimization of $\text{LiI}@n\text{H}_2$ ($n=1-10$), we have used the LanL2DZ basis set.

5.3. HOMO, LUMO, HOMO–LUMO energy gap

The HOMO and LUMO types of molecular orbitals are used in chemistry. "HOMO" stands for "Highest occupied molecular orbital," while "LUMO" means "Lowest unoccupied molecular orbital." The highest energy molecular orbital is the HOMO, which is full of electrons. The next highest energy orbital is the LUMO, which is empty. The HOMO–LUMO energy gap is the difference in energy between the HOMO and the LUMO. The difference in energy between these two orbitals can be used to predict the strength and stability of metal complexes. Higher is the difference higher is the stability. For example, here we have given HOMO and LUMO structure, their corresponding energy, and the HOMO–LUMO energy gap of LiI and its H_2 adsorbed systems [Fig. 1].

Optimized structures	HOMO	LUMO	$\Delta E_{(\text{HOMO-LUMO})}$
<p>$E_0 = -0.59$ eV</p>	- 7.42 eV		
<p>$E_0 = 0.22$ eV</p>	- 8.19 eV		
	- 8.81 eV		

<p>$E_0 = -580.77 \text{ eV}$</p>		<p>$E_0 = 0.88 \text{ eV}$</p>	
<p>$E_0 = 0.91 \text{ eV}$</p>	<p>- 8.79 eV</p>		
<p>$E_0 = 0.51 \text{ eV}$</p>	<p>- 8.35 eV</p>		
<p>$E_0 = 0.56 \text{ eV}$</p>	<p>- 8.42 eV</p>		
<p>$E_0 = 0.65 \text{ eV}$</p>	<p>- 8.54 eV</p>		
<p>$E_0 = 0.61 \text{ eV}$</p>	<p>- 8.52 eV</p>		

<p>E₀ = 1.26 eV</p>	- 9.10 eV		
<p>E₀ = 1.29 eV</p>	- 9.16 eV		
<p>E₀ = 1.29 eV</p>	- 9.19 eV		

Fig. 1. Optimized geometries, ground state energy, point group, HOMO, LUMO, and $\Delta E_{\text{HOMO-LUMO}}$ (eV) of LiI and LiI @nH₂ [n= 1-10] molecule at the ω B97X-D /LanL2DZ level of theory.

5.4. Hardness (η), electronegativity (χ), and electrophilicity (ω)

In this work, mathematical reactivity functions, sometimes called reactivity descriptors, are developed to describe chemical reactivity between interacting molecules. Conceptual DFT and its global reactivity descriptors like hardness (η),^[36] electronegativity (χ),^[37] and electrophilicity (ω)^[38] are derived from qualitative theories. Pauling^[39] came up with the word "electronegativity" (χ), which means the "power" of an atom in a molecule to pull bonded electrons toward itself. Mulliken^[40] also said that electronegativity (χ) is a function of the two main experimentally determined parameters of a system, which are the first ionization energy (IE) and the electron affinity (EA). He showed that χ can be written as the arithmetic mean of the IP and EA values. Thus, according to Mulliken^[41]

$$\chi = \frac{IE+EA}{2} \quad (1)$$

The concept of molecular hardness was proposed quantitatively in the form of a mathematical descriptor by Parr and Pearson,^[42] who defined chemical hardness for a molecular system is the first derivative of the chemical potential (μ) or the second derivative of energy (E) as a function of the number of electrons, N, at a constant external potential $v(r)$

$$\eta = \left(\frac{\partial \mu}{\partial N} \right)_{v(r)} = \left(\frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial N^2} \right)_{v(r)} \quad (2)$$

The convex shape in the E vs. N curve renders the value of η to keep on positive and from the finite-difference method, the corresponding curvature equals $IE - EA$, which signifies hardness. Therefore-

$$\eta = \left(\frac{\partial \mu}{\partial N} \right)_{v(r)} = \left(\frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial N^2} \right)_{v(r)} \approx IP - EA \quad (3)$$

The electrophilicity index (ω)^[43] as given by Parr et al. is

$$\omega = \frac{\mu^2}{2\eta} = \frac{\chi^2}{2\eta} \quad (4)$$

Here we have considered LiI and its H₂ adsorbed systems as an example for our study on these parameters. Now from Fig. 2, it is clear that hardness (η) and electrophilicity (ω) gradually increased and decreased respectively. There is a direct relation between hardness and stability and indirect relation between electrophilicity and reactivity. So from this result, we can summarise that stability will increase and reactivity will increase respectively upon gradual H₂ adsorption.

Fig. 2. Plot of Hardness (η), electronegativity (χ), and electrophilicity (ω) [eV] vs. no. of H₂ molecules trapped in LiI@nH₂ systems at the ω B97X-D /LanL2DZ level of theory

5.5. Average adsorption energy (E_{ads})/H₂ and adsorption ability (E_r)

For an H₂ storage system, the average adsorption energy (E_{ads})/H₂^[44-48] is a parameter by which we can predict the mode of adsorption process is either physical adsorption or chemical adsorption, or quasi-sorption. For LiI@nH₂ systems, it can be expressed as-

$$E_{ads}/H_2 = [E_{LiI+nH_2} - nE_{H_2} - E_{LiI}]/n \quad (5)$$

where E_{LiI+nH_2} , E_{LiI} , and E_{H_2} are energies of the H₂ adsorbed LiI systems, LiI building block, and H₂ molecule respectively. n represents the number of adsorbed H₂ molecules respectively. In the case of physisorption, the average adsorption energy (E_{ads})/H₂ lies in the meV range. In the case of chemisorption, the average adsorption energy (E_{ads})/H₂ lies in the 2-4 eV range. In the case of quasi-sorption, the average adsorption energy (E_{ads})/H₂ lies in the 0.1-0.8 eV range. Now from Table 1, we can say that LiI has obeyed the quasi-sorption process during H₂ adsorption.

Again the adsorption ability (E_r)^[44-48] is another parameter by the value of which we can understand whether the subsequent H₂ adsorption will occur or not. When E_r is positive, it reflects that building blocks will adsorb H₂ molecules, but when the value of E_r is very small or negative, it suggests that adsorption of H₂ molecules will be difficult. For LiI@nH₂ systems, it can be expressed as-

$$E_r = [E_{\text{LiI}@(n-1)\text{H}_2} + E_{\text{H}_2} - E_{\text{LiI}@\text{nH}_2}] \quad (6)$$

$$E_r = [E_{\text{LiI}@(n-2)\text{H}_2} + 2E_{\text{H}_2} - E_{\text{LiI}@\text{nH}_2}] \quad (7)$$

As the E_r result for $\text{LiI}@\text{nH}_2$ systems is shown in Table 1 decreases after that its value is very small which we can neglect. Thus we have considered LiI can adsorb a maximum of 10 H_2 molecules.

Table 1. Average adsorption energy/ H_2 and adsorption ability of $\text{LiI}@\text{nH}_2$ systems at $\omega\text{B97X-D/LanL2DZ}$ level of theory.

Systems	Average adsorption energy ($E_{\text{ads}}/\text{H}_2$)	Adsorption ability (E_r)
$\text{LiI}@\text{H}_2$	0.16	0.16
$\text{LiI}@\text{2H}_2$	0.16	0.16
$\text{LiI}@\text{3H}_2$	0.17	0.17
$\text{LiI}@\text{4H}_2$	0.16	0.15
$\text{LiI}@\text{5H}_2$	0.14	0.05
$\text{LiI}@\text{6H}_2$	0.13	0.05
$\text{LiI}@\text{7H}_2$	0.12	0.06
$\text{LiI}@\text{8H}_2$	0.12	0.13
$\text{LiI}@\text{9H}_2$	0.11	0.05
$\text{LiI}@\text{10H}_2$	0.10	0.06

5.6. Natural bond orbital (NBO) charge

Quantum chemistry studies aim to determine each polyatomic molecule's electronic arrangement and net charge. Chemical interpretation of the wave function requires knowledge

of atomic charge distributions, leading to a better understanding and correlation of chemical events. Even with exact wave functions, it's difficult to measure "atomic charge" and "orbital populations."^[49] Only Mulliken's population analysis approach is widely used. Mulliken populations fail to reliably characterize charge distribution in many circumstances, as noted in the literature. Mulliken's population analysis has three objections.

- Populations of Mulliken's can have negative values that don't make sense. If the values were small, this flaw might be easy to overlook, but sometimes the values are quite big.
- Mulliken populations are too sensitive to the basis set, especially as the basis set gets bigger to make it more accurate.
- Mulliken's calculations seem to give an unrealistic picture of how charges are distributed in compounds with a lot of ionic character. A study by Collins and Streitwieser on different organic and inorganic lithium compounds can be used as an example. These researchers found that the Mulliken charge on lithium is very different (by up to 0.7 e) from what would be expected based on other factors. In some cases, this led to charges with the opposite sign from what would be expected based on differences in electronegativity. They conclude that "Mulliken populations with Li compounds are not reliable at all and shouldn't be taken seriously." A technique of "natural population analysis" may determine atomic charges and orbital populations of molecular wave functions in generic atomic orbital basis sets. The natural analysis is an alternative to standard Mulliken population analysis and appears to have greater numerical stability and explain the electron distribution in compounds

with strong ionic character, such as those with metal atoms. The natural charge also called the "NPA" charge, and "NBO charge" are the same thing. The formulations for Mulliken charge and NPA charge are basically the same. The main difference is that the Mulliken charge is calculated using original basis functions, while the NPA charge is based on natural atomic orbitals (NAOs). Here we have taken LiI and LiI@nH₂ systems for evaluation of NBO charge before H₂ adsorption and after one by one H₂ adsorption. From Table 2 we can see that before H₂ adsorption charge on Li of LiI is 0.861 after that with the progress of gradual H₂ adsorption this value decreases and comes down to 0.762 for the LiI@10H₂ system. Again from this Table 2, we can see that charge has developed on H atoms of adsorbed H₂ molecules. This is due to dipole-induced dipole interaction between Li centre and adsorbed H₂ molecules respectively. Also, the decrease of NBO charge on Li centre after gradual H₂ adsorption has a direct influence on the decrease of average adsorption energy/H₂. When the charge on Li centre will decrease the efficiency of the formation of the induced dipole on adsorbed H₂ molecules will decrease as a result dipole-induced dipole interaction will gradually decrease thus there is a downtrend of average adsorption energy/H₂.

5.7. Gravimetric wt%

Among many parameters, gravimetric wt% [44-48] is one of the important parameters upon which the ideal nature of the hydrogen storage materials depends. We can calculate gravimetric wt% by considering the following equation.

$$\text{Gravimetric wt\%} = \frac{\text{MW of trapped H}_2}{\text{MW of thiazole-Li}^+\text{@nH}_2\text{ complex}} \times 100 \quad (8)$$

[MW = molecular weight]

For ideal hydrogen storage materials, the U.S. Department of Energy (DOE)^[26] has fixed the values of gravimetric wt% (6.0% in 2010 and 9.0% in 2015). In the case of the LiI@10H₂ system, we got 13.07% (Table 2) which is very much satisfied with respect to the U.S. DOE target value.

Table 2. Gravimetric wt% and NBO charge on Li centre of LiI@nH₂ systems at ωB97X-D /LanL2DZ level of theory.

Systems	Gravimetric wt%	NBO charge on Li centre
LiI		0.861
LiI@H ₂	1.48	0.832
LiI@2H ₂	2.92	0.808
LiI@3H ₂	4.32	0.782
LiI@4H ₂	5.67	0.78
LiI@5H ₂	6.99	0.78
LiI@6H ₂	8.28	0.778
LiI@7H ₂	9.52	0.778
LiI@8H ₂	10.74	0.764
LiI@9H ₂	11.92	0.763
LiI@10H ₂	13.07	0.762
LiBr@10H ₂	18.71	[Ref. 28]
LiCl@10H ₂	32	[Ref. 28]
LiF@10H ₂	43.48	[Ref. 27]

5.8. Bonding Nature

The electron localization function (ELF)^[50] in quantum chemistry is a measure of the

probability of locating an electron in the neighborhood space of a reference electron situated at a particular position and with the same spin. Physically, this determines the extent of the reference electron's spatial localization and gives a way for mapping electron pair probability in multielectronic systems. In chemistry, topology^[51] describes and predicts the molecule structure within the restrictions of three-dimensional (3-D) space. Given the determinants of chemical bonding and the chemical characteristics of the atoms, topology explains how the ethereal wave functions of the atoms must fit together. Bader uses quantum mechanics to explain what a bond is and where it is. In his book "Atoms in Molecules (AIM)^[52,53]: A Quantum Theory" [Bader, 1990], commonly known as "the quantum theory of atoms in molecules" (QTAIM),^[52,53] he uses quantum mechanics to explain all the basic ideas in chemistry, such as atoms, molecules, and chemical bonds. To achieve this, he separates molecules into atomic quantum subsystems. The electron density topology defines one atom from the next. Each subsystem (or atom) has a surface where the electron density gradient vector field [$\rho(r_c)$] has no flow. Bader discusses 4 crucial spots in 3 dimensions using electron density topology.

- **(3, -3) critical point-** In each of the three perpendicular directions of space, the electron density falls. This point represents a local maximum in the electron density.
- **(3, -1) critical point-** In two of space's perpendicular directions, the density of electrons decreases, while it increases in the third. Maximum electron density is found in two spatial directions and minimal in a third at this saddle point.
- **(3, +1) critical point-** In one direction, the density of electrons decreases while it increases in the other two orthogonal directions. Once again, this is a saddle point, where the value is greatest in one direction and the least in the other two.
- **(3, +3) critical point-** This is a local minimum with electron density rising in all 3 directions of space.

Is there a connection between these points and chemistry in any way? Here is some description of the chemical meaning of these points:

- **(3, -3) critical point-** At this coordinate system, one atom can be found. Also, all atoms outside of hydrogen have their nuclei there. Thus, the location is also known as a critical point in the atomic scale.
- **(3, -1) critical point-** This point is between two atoms that are close to each other and makes a bond between them. This point is also called a bond critical point because of this.
- **(3, +1) critical point-** This point is located in the centre of a ring that is composed of many bonds. It is also known as a ring critical point in some circles.
- **(3, +3) critical point-** Since this is the point at which numerous rings converge to create a cage, it is referred to as a cage critical point.

Multiwfn is a very effective tool for analyzing electronic wavefunctions, a crucial component of quantum chemistry. This function analyses electron density, its Laplacian, orbital wavefunction, and spin density.

For example, we used topological analysis of the LiI@H₂ system at the bond critical point (BCP) to find the bonding nature determining parameters like electron density [$\rho(r_c)$], Laplacian of electron density [$\nabla^2\rho(r_c)$], local electron energy density [$H(r_c)$], kinetic energy density [$G(r_c)$], and potential energy density [$v(r_c)$].^[52,53] We created three figures to demonstrate the bonding nature of LiI@H₂ using the multiwfn program.^[54] The top and bottom halves of Fig. 3a show how the electron density varies. No electron density is seen between the Li core and the adsorbed H₂ molecule. This supports the ionic bonding between the Li center and the adsorbed H₂ molecules.

Fig. 3a. Shaded surface map with the projection of the electron density of the LiI@H₂ system generated at the ω B97X-D /LanL2DZ level of theory. **Fig. 3b.** Contour plot of the Laplacian of the electron density of the LiI@H₂ system generated at the ω B97X-D /LanL2DZ level of theory. **Fig. 3c.** The plot of the ELF of the LiI@H₂ systems generated at the ω B97X-D /LanL2DZ level of theory.

In Fig. 3b the green solid lines indicate the area of the charge depletion ($\nabla^2 \rho(r) > 0$), and the blue dotted lines indicate areas of the charge concentration ($\nabla^2 \rho(r) < 0$).^[55,56] The atomic nuclei connected by the brown solid lines represent the bond paths, and the atomic nuclei separated by the solid bold blue lines indicate the zero-flux surfaces in the molecular plane. Light blue spheres are the points where the bond paths and zero-flux surfaces cross each other called the bond critical points (BCPs). There is no electron density between Li and the adsorbed H₂ molecule suggests ionic bonding. The electron localization function (ELF) in quantum chemistry is a measure of the probability of locating an electron in the neighborhood space of

a reference electron situated at a particular position and with the same spin. Physically, this determines the extent of the reference electron's spatial localization and gives a way for mapping electron pair probability in multielectronic systems.^[55,56] Fig. 3c shows the electron localization function (ELF) of the LiI@H₂ system. There is no localized electron in between Li and the adsorbed H₂ molecule in this image suggests ionic bonding.

Now one can predict the nature of the bond from the value of $[-G(r)/V(r)]$. Which is stated below^[55,56] -

- (i) When $[-G(r)/V(r)] > 1$ then the interaction is said to be non-covalent.
- (ii) When $0.5 < -G(r)/V(r) < 1$ then the interaction is said to be partially covalent and

Now the strength of this interaction depends on the sign of both $\nabla^2 \rho$ and $H(r)$. Which is specified below-

- a) When the sign of both $\nabla^2 \rho$ and $H(r)$ is negative then the interaction is said to be quite strong.
- b) When the sign of $H(r)$ is negative and the sign of $\nabla^2 \rho$ positive then the interaction is said to be medium.
- c) When the sign of both $\nabla^2 \rho$ and $H(r)$ is positive then the interaction is said to be weak.

As in that case (LiI@H₂) [Table 3] the negative ratio of $-G(r_c)$ and $V(r_c)$ is larger than 1 and the sign of both $\nabla^2 \rho(r_c)$ and $H(r_c)$ are positive (0.04 and 0.003) so we can conclude that LiI...H₂ interactions are non-covalent type but interaction is weak in nature.

Table 3. Electron Density Descriptors (au) at the BCPs of hydrogen and the LiI complex obtained from the wave functions generated at the ω B97X-D/LanL2DZ level of theory.

BCP	$\rho(r_c)$	$\nabla^2 \rho(r_c)$	$G(r_c)$	$V(r_c)$	$H(r_c)$	$-G(r_c)/V(r_c)$
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LiI @ nH ₂	0.006	0.04	0.006	-0.003	0.003	2
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5.9. Spontaneity temperature

The temperature-dependent spontaneity^[44-48,57] of this H₂ storing process can be done by deriving the Gibbs free energy change (ΔG). From thermodynamics, it is well known that when its value will be negative then we can say that the adsorption process is spontaneous. For that purpose, we have obeyed the following equation by taking LiI as an example.

$$\Delta G_{\text{LiI}@n\text{H}_2} = G_{\text{LiI}@n\text{H}_2} - G_{\text{LiI}} - nG_{\text{H}_2} \quad (9)$$

Here $G_{\text{LiI}@n\text{H}_2}$, G_{LiI} , and nG_{H_2} indicate Gibbs free energy of the H₂ adsorbed LiI systems, LiI systems, and adsorbed H₂ molecules respectively. Our group has already reported LiF can adsorb H₂ spontaneously at 54K or below this temperature. We have also worked on LiCl and LiBr systems. For those systems we have determined at 49K or below this temperature H₂ adsorption process will be spontaneous. Using previous experience, we have started checking of Gibbs free energy change of H₂ adsorbed LiI systems ($\Delta G_{\text{LiI}@n\text{H}_2}$) at 54 K temperature. But the result shows that at 44 K the value of Gibbs free energy change for all LiI@(1-10)H₂ systems started to turn negative. Which has been shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Gibbs free energy change (eV) for hydrogen adsorption of LiI@nH₂ systems at different temperatures calculated at the ω B97X-D/LanL2DZ level of theory.

Systems	n	Temperature (K)			
		54K	49K	45K	44K
LiI@nH ₂	1	-1.048	-1.059	-1.080	-1.097
	2	-0.983	-0.997	-1.021	-1.038
	3	-0.913	-0.930	-0.957	-0.975
	4	-0.777	-0.799	-0.829	-0.848
	5	-0.629	-0.654	-0.687	-0.706
	6	-0.482	-0.510	-0.544	-0.564
	7	-0.341	-0.372	-0.410	-0.431
	8	-0.190	-0.226	-0.268	-0.290
	9	-0.035	-0.075	-0.120	-0.142
	10	0.102	0.058	0.012	-0.011

Conclusions

The LiI molecules are acknowledged as promising hydrogen storage templates since the quasi-sorption process is supported by their adsorption energy [average adsorption energy (E_{ads}/H_2)]. The NBO analysis shows that the positive charge on the Li atom reduces across the whole system with the adsorption of H₂ molecules. It supports the dipole-induced dipole interaction. Comparing the U.S.DOE (2015) standard, a single LiI molecule is capable of adsorbing 10 H₂ with a high gravimetric wt% value (13.07 for LiI). The LiI building unit attracts the H₂ molecules by electrovalent interactions, in accordance with the atoms in molecules (AIM) analysis. The changes in Gibbs free energy (ΔG) show that the process of hydrogen adsorption is spontaneous at or below 44K.

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